

HOW TOUGH ARE FIBROUS COMPOSITES ?

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SUMMARY

There continue spectacular failures during the early service life of very high performance fibre composites. So it seems worthwhile to recall the early experiments and ideas by the authors and many others developed between 1965 and 1973 which contribute to adequate toughness. That composites can be as tough as metals is shown. Following this a suggestion is made that Poissons ratio be used as a diagnostic parameter for fatigue of laminate

Toughness, damage mechanics, notches, history, fatigue Poissons ratio

INTRODUCTION

Despite the current wide spread use of fibre composites (e.g. in the Boeing 787 where 80% of the volume and more than 50% of the weight of the airframe is made with fibre reinforced resin) there still occur from time to time spectacular failure of stressed composite components (Philips catamaran, the tail fin and rudder of the American Airlines aircraft flight 587 and many formula one crashes).

At the time that very stiff fibres were invented in the early 1960s there still remained vividly in the collective engineering memory the catastrophic failure of welded Liberty Ships during WW2 and the Comet disaster only shortly after. It followed that the idea of a viable engineering material containing two brittle materials appeared to run counter to common sense.

The paper will deal with laminates starting with **the crack tip** showing that the driving force necessary for extension normal to the fibres (trans-fibre or trans-laminar failure), for a deep crack, must be the observed mode even though the resistance to propagation along the fibres is usually much less

LARGE AND SMALL NOTCHES

In the early years, the distinction between large (deep) notches and small ones was difficult to unravel. but the widespread use of CFRP led to clear quantitative distinction during the early 70s. For large notches, the observed fracture stress was found to be consistent with a stress concentration factor predicted by elastic analyses which took into account the elastic anisotropy of the material, but for small notches the tensile stress at the notch tip indicated by the elastic analysis became considerably greater than the composite tensile strength..

The distinction was clarified in the mid 1970s by work at Farnborough and other places; Potter [1] argued that immediately ahead of a broken fibre, shear parallel to the fibres accompanied, perhaps, by plastic flow and failure of the matrix and of the interface, will limit the stress concentration upon the first unbroken fibre . The concentrated applied stress varies across the section and so failure of the second fibre will only occur if, on failure of the first fibre under stress σ_f , the stress on the second fibre is within a small

quantity $\Delta\sigma_f$ of this. Potter assumed that $\Delta\sigma_f$ is a characteristic constant for distinguishing large and small notches and the successful application will be described. Small notches are characterised by the formation of stable damage zones which form at the end of the notch when the local tensile strength is reached. The investigation of these damage zones in composites is now a major activity of academic composite research known as Damage Mechanics [2]. The present contribution reviews.

CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE WORK OF FRACTURE

These are due to: matrix deformation; fibre pull out and debonding of fibre and matrix. The toughness due to each is summarised quantitatively. Comparing values obtained by pull-out with those found in other tough high strength materials we find for CFRP a work of fracture of $4.5 \times 10^3 \text{J/m}^2$ for a material with a breaking strength of $\approx 1.5 \text{GPa}$. This compares with a high strength maraging steel of similar strength, but, very much higher density, of about $7 \times 10^3 \text{J/m}^2$ - hence of much the same order. Multiple fracture a name for the general finding that when loaded in flexure or in tension most types of fibre composite show a load-elongation curve where an initial elastic almost linear portion is followed by curve where cracking occurs. This phenomenon will be briefly analysed and shown to lead to the concept of The constrained crack [3]. Finally experiments on the crushing of tubes demonstrate that fibrous composites can show works of fracture per unit of weight which exceed the performance of metals

FATIGUE OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

For most laminates in service the effect, under load, of notches or sharp changes of section is understood. However the specimens usually undergo fatigue. In general the nature of the damage produced by cyclic loading is complicated because many types of damage can be observed, for instance: film fracture, matrix cracking, fibre buckling, longitudinal splitting, ply delamination etc. Even for a precisely defined composite structure it is usually not known which type of damage is the most significant. Because of the many uncertainties with composites, designs for specific components are grossly "overdesigned". We have personally seen this happen with excessive "safety" or "uncertainty" factors being applied to the composite material. In contrast to the metal case where fatigue is not accompanied by a marked change in the elastic constants, composite laminates deteriorate through breaking of fibres, shear, debonding and the formation of cracks within the material. There is therefore a decrease in density and an increase in permeability and a loss of stiffness. We suggest that the measurement of Poissons ratios of a composite component could be used as an index of the damage since it is sensitive both to loss of shear stiffness and to increase in compressibility due to cracking and is known to change (usually to decrease) proportionally more than the stiffnesses. An elastically orthotropic laminate of, say, a high performance carbon fibre in epoxy resin, possesses 3 independent values of Poissons ratio- the paper will discuss which Poissons ratio is best to monitor in a particular case.

References

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- [3] Kelly A (1996) Phil. Trans. R Soc. Lond. **374** 1841-1874